

A Study of Hearing Impaired Children in Relation to their Emotional Maturity

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Abstract Researches show low level of emotional maturity among the hearing impaired children. This low level of emotional maturity among hearing impaired children may be attributed to their restricted opportunities of self expression. Hearing loss has negative effects on a person's inter and intra personal relations and emotional well being also. The reported low level of emotional maturity among hearing impaired children may result in many different issues and may also restrict their academic excellence. So, the present study aims to study the relationship between academic achievement and emotional maturity of male and female hearing impaired children. To achieve this objective a survey study was conducted on 184 hearing impaired children studying in the two different Sanket schools of UP government. Findings revealed significant positive correlation between the emotional maturity and academic achievement of both male and female hearing impaired children.

Keywords Hearing Impaired Children, Emotional Maturity, and Academic Achievement.

Introduction Researches show low level of emotional maturity among the hearing impaired children. Farrugia and Austin (1980) who concluded that hearing impaired students of public schools are at lower levels in emotional and emotional behaviors. Similarly Pujar and Patil (2019) found majority of the hearing impaired students studying in secondary classes at low level and a few at moderate. This low level of emotional maturity among hearing impaired children may be attributed to their restricted opportunities of self expression. Hearing loss has negative effects on a person's inter and intra personal relations and emotional well being also. Hearing loss in the early childhood may even cause greater emotional challenges. It may decrease their self esteem and can cause behavioral problems even at home. They may feel isolated and fearful about their inability to communicate resulting in losing their relations social standing which may have a huge emotional effects (ngsolutions.com) Understanding the emotional impact of hearing loss on children & adults). Hurt and Gonzalez (1988) also support that hearing impaired children often feel apprehensive about communication and are less able to express their emotions verbally (Maxon, 1991).

Aim of study The reported low level of emotional maturity among hearing impaired children may result in many different issues and may also restrict their academic excellence. So, based on this argument the present paper aims:

1. To study the relationship between academic achievement and emotional maturity of hearing impaired children.
2. To study the relationship between academic achievement and emotional maturity of male hearing impaired children.
3. To study the relationship between academic achievement and emotional maturity of female hearing impaired children.

Review of Literature

Similar to the findings of present study significant positive correlation was found between emotional maturity and academic achievement of adolescent students by Rukmini and Ramaswamy (2021). Dhami (1974) also examined in his study that intelligence, emotional maturity and financial status as element characteristics of achievement of secondary students of Punjab. To support Muley, Patnam, and Vasekar (2003) found high positive correlation between emotional maturity and academic achievement of school going children of urban area. Similarly, Chaturvedi and Kumari (2012) concluded that that

emotional maturity has huge impact on academic achievement of male higher secondary students. Further Shanmuganathan and Chinnappan (2014) investigated a critical relation between the emotional maturity and academic achievement of young adult students in his study.

Methodology To achieve the research objective the most suitable method was normative survey method, also known as survey or descriptive survey. Population- All the hearing impaired children studying in 6th to 10th classes in special schools of UP government named as 'Sanket' constitute the population for present study. There are 5 Sankets in UP and are special schools for hearing impaired students There were 790 hearing impaired students enrolled in these schools.

Sampling

A representative sample of 184 hearing impaired children studying in junior high school and high school level was selected using purposive sampling for the study. Maintaining a balance between the number of students studying in the two different levels of education 120 hearing impaired children were selected from the junior high school classes and 64 (as found in the selected school) from the high school level. Children at junior high school level were selected on the basis of their regularity in the school.

Tools Used

To measure the emotional maturity of hearing impaired children 'Emotional Maturity Scale' developed by Yashvir Singh was used. And to gather information about the academic achievement of hearing impaired students previous class result of the selected children was used.

Statistics Used in the Study

Pearson's Product Moment Correlation(r) was used to find out the correlation coefficient between academic achievement and emotional maturity of hearing impaired children.

Analysis

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between academic achievement and emotional maturity of hearing impaired children.

Table 1. Relationship between Academic Achievement and Emotional Maturity of Hearing Impaired Children

Variables	N	r Value	Significance (p-value)
Academic Achievement	184	.267	.000
Emotional Maturity			

Table 1 depicts the correlation between academic achievement and emotional maturity of hearing impaired children. The calculated correlation coefficient is 0.267 ($p = .000 < .05$) that is significant at 0.05 level of confidence. Thus, null hypothesis that "There is no significant relationship between academic achievement and emotional maturity of hearing impaired children" is rejected and it is inferred that there is a significant and positive relationship between academic achievement and emotional maturity of hearing impaired children. Correlation between academic achievement and emotional maturity of hearing impaired children is presented in figure 1.

Figure 1 Bar Graph Showing the r Value of Academic Achievement and Emotional Maturity of Hearing Impaired Children

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between academic achievement and emotional maturity of male hearing impaired children.

Table 2 Relationship between Academic Achievement and Emotional Maturity of Male Hearing Impaired Children

Variables	N	r Value	Significance (p-value)
Academic Achievement Emotional Maturity of Male Hearing Impaired Children	128	.260	.003

The above table 2 depicts the correlation between academic achievement and emotional maturity of male hearing impaired children. The calculated correlation coefficient is 0.260 ($p = .003 < .05$) that is significant at 0.05 level of confidence. Therefore, null hypothesis that “There is no significant relationship between academic achievement and emotional maturity of male hearing impaired children” is rejected and it is inferred that there is a significant and positive relationship between academic achievement and emotional maturity of male hearing impaired children. Correlation between academic achievement and emotional maturity of male hearing impaired children is presented in figure 2.

Figure 2 Bar Graph Showing the r Value of Academic Achievement and Emotional Maturity of Male Hearing Impaired Children

H03: There is no significant relationship between academic achievement and emotional maturity of female hearing impaired children.

Table 3 Relationship between Academic Achievement and Emotional Maturity of Female Hearing Impaired Children

Variables	N	r Value	Significance
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			(p-value)
Academic Achievement	56	.296	.026
Emotional Maturity of Female Hearing Impaired Children			

The above table 3 depicts the correlation between academic achievement and emotional maturity of female hearing impaired children. The calculated correlation coefficient is 0.296 ($p = .026 < .05$) that is significant at 0.05 level of confidence. Therefore, null hypothesis that “There is no significant relationship between academic achievement and emotional maturity of female hearing impaired children” is rejected and it is inferred that there is a significant and positive relationship between academic achievement and emotional maturity of female hearing impaired children. Correlation between academic achievement and emotional maturity of female hearing impaired children is presented in figure 3.

Figure 3 Bar Graph Showing the r Value of Academic Achievement and Emotional Maturity of Female Hearing Impaired Children

Findings

1. A significant and positive relationship was observed between academic achievement and emotional maturity of hearing impaired children. Hence it is concluded that academic achievement of hearing impaired children go with their emotional maturity and vice versa.
2. A significant and positive relationship was observed between academic achievement and emotional maturity of male hearing impaired children. Hence it is concluded that academic achievement of male hearing impaired children, go with their emotional maturity and vice versa.
3. A significant and positive relationship was observed between academic achievement and emotional maturity of female hearing impaired children. Hence it is concluded that academic achievement of female hearing impaired children, go with their emotional maturity and vice versa.

Conclusion

Here, it becomes clear how important it is to improve the level of the emotional maturity of hearing impaired children. To improve their level, components of life skills should be added in the curriculum of special schools of UP by text book developers and policy makers. Text books should be updated by incorporating the motivating stories and examples from ancient Indian literature and daily life. This may be done by incorporating situation based problems in the text books also. Besides, some training based interactive sessions may be arranged for these children. These sessions must be activity based and provide best suitable situations to the children with needed assistance where they can learn how to handle particular situations in a practical way. The teachers teaching hearing impaired children should need to be more sensitive towards the emotional needs of these children. They need to be more careful about the selection of their teaching methods, strategies, and techniques for teaching these children. Accordingly, they should select and mould their motivation strategies and disciplinary approaches for these children.

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